

Post-media challenges to the political narrative of respect, reverence and rule

Soma Basu

AJK Mass Communication and Research Centre,
Jamia Millia Islamia, New Delhi, India
Email: letters2soma@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

The article, while delineating the ‘demand for respect’ for political leaders in the contemporary media narrative, delineates the rubric of policing political expression and protest language of the masses and how it conforms to the older forms of persuasion. Through an analysis of online media texts, the article then limns the disjunctures in this sovereignty through newer languages of online memes and the absurdity of future mediascape.

Keywords: Respect, persuasion, hegemony, iconography, post-media, memes, protest language

1. Introduction

On January 7, 2020, Amish Devgan, an Indian television news anchor of CNN-News 18 India, a prominent Hindi mainstream television news channel, launched a diatribe in his primetime show ‘Aar Paar’ against people participating in an Anti-Citizenship Amendment Act (anti-CAA) demonstration in Mumbai for carrying posters and placards with “abusive words” against the Prime Minister Narendra Modi and Home Minister Amit Shah¹.

The posters and placards couldn’t be seen in the video that rolled along with the anchor’s harangue since they were masked or edited out. During his show, the anchor aggressively questioned the language of protest. His main assertion emerged to be that the Prime Minister and Home Minister, or any other senior political leader should not ‘respected’ and use of NSFW (not safe for work) language in protests not just equals to exhibiting obscenity in public but also borderline seditious. In doing so, he also attempted to portray the protest as a cite of obscenity detrimental to the social fabric that Indians should aspire for. The clip of the anchor was edited out of the programme video and shared with a variety of comments and tweets on social media, with different contexts. A Indian National Congress (INC) party spokesperson, Rajiv Tyagi, had used two specific NSFW words against the anchor on a live show for his bias towards the ruling Bhartiya Janta Party (BJP)². The two words fused into the online subculture in such a way that whenever there is a mention of the anchor, the two words are also used in some context or the other.

¹ Video clip of the show retrieved from YouTube <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=3PdpPdXdHo4&t=18s>

² Video clip of the show retrieved from YouTube <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=aPA-qlyIrGg>

So, the anchor's haranguing over language used against political leaders, he has been known to support unabashedly, led to a gush of memes online and the show ended up deriving a completely different meaning altogether.

The drift of the show was soon followed by Zee News, one of the leading news channel, that ran a show on January 16, 2020, titled "Kabhi neech, kabhi kaatil, kabhi ranga billa?"³ (Lowly, Murderer, Ranga Billa?). The anchor bracketed all who opposed the policies of the Prime Minister as 'Anti-Nationals' and concluded that these 'anti-nationals' used the derisive language to discredit the 'good work' that the Prime Minister was doing for the country.

This is how media propagates 'banal nationalism' (Billig, 1995) by continuously flagging an idea of 'nationalism' through routine symbols and habits of language. The two TV news channels could be seen problematizing the language of protest and consolidating the idea of respecting political leaders.

While the two debates ran in the confines of a studio and trickled out to social media, since January 21, 2020, 85 children, their parents and teachers were being interrogated by police for a play on CAA staged in a school in Bidar, Karnataka, as a part of a curriculum on social awareness⁴.

A parent attending the play had live-streamed it on Facebook and one of user lodged a first information report (FIR) claiming that certain dialogues of the play were "derogatory to the Indian prime minister Narendra Modi". The children were spared because of the Juvenile Justice Act (2015) but mother of a 11-

³ Video clip of the show retrieved from Facebook <https://www.facebook.com/watch/?v=607984993329255>

⁴ Shreyas HR (Feb 6, 2020). Bidar cops interrogate 85 school kids 5 times over 9 days for 'anti-CAA play, Times of India. Retrieved from <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/india/bidar-cops-interrogate-85-school-kids-5-times-over-9-days-for-anti-cao-play/articleshow/73977593.cms>

year-old student was arrested. The student had played the role of an old woman in the skit where 11ia proliferation.

Father of new India

Any nationalist storyline has a father-figure or a singular hero as a protagonist. The personalistic leader-as-icon appears in a range of authoritarian regimes, and it is materially inscribed in the symbolic landscapes to create the impression of unity among elites and the masses (Koch, 2016).

Even though Mahatma Gandhi was never officially accorded with a title⁵, he is known as the ‘Father of India’ because of his contribution toward freeing India from the British colonial rule. With the 2014 election campaign slogan, “Acche Din Aane Wale Ha (Good days are ahead)”, the Bharatiya Janta Party (BJP) was promising a ‘new’ corruption-free, pro-development India.

Narendra Modi was chosen to lead this ‘new India’ into ‘achhe din’ but the leader continued to be haunted by his past - the Godhra riots of 2002 in Gujarat during his chief ministership. A 2014 Reuters article, called the new Prime Minister a “control freak”⁶. From various administrative reshuffling to work on public holidays to launching surveillance systems for government officials. Foucault had said, “the body becomes a useful force, only if it is both a productive body and a subjected body.”

The desire to control did not stay restricted to his office. It leaked out to the masses through the party’s IT (information technology cell)⁷, through aggressive drive to get the citizens biometrics cards and through series of other plans and policies that would centralise control over citizen data and eventually the citizens themselves.

As Edmund Leach said, “Social control and social cohesion is produced within bounded societies”, and kin terminology, if successfully manipulated, can bring elicit nepotistic behaviour (Johnson, 1986, 1987). This ‘new India’ needed a ‘new father’ to look up to, whose ideology would be syncretic to the ruling Party. Hegemony in any political context is fragile and requires renewal and modification through the assertion and reassertion of power. (Williams & Hall, 1977).

It was Amruta Fadnavis, wife of former chief minister of Maharashtra Devendra Fadnavis, who first called Narendra Modi, father of India. She tweeted on September 17, 2019: “Wishing the Father of our Country @narendramodi ji a very Happy Birthday - who inspires us to work relentlessly towards the betterment of the society !”

⁵ Jaiswal A (Jan 20, 2020). Mahatma Gandhi was never declared ‘Father of Nation’, reveals RTI reply, Times of India, retrieved from <https://timesofindia.indiatimes.com/india/mahatma-gandhi-was-never-declared-father-of-nation-reveals-rti-reply/articleshow/73446044.cms>

⁶ Busvine D (Oct 9, 2014). India's Prime Minister Is A Control Freak, Business Insider/Reuters. Retrieved from <https://www.businessinsider.com/r-big-brother-modi-is-watching-indias-bureaucrats-2014-10?IR=T>

⁷ Chaturvedi S (2016). “I Am A Troll”, Juggernaut Books; ISBN 9789386228093

The tweet was shared 1,000 times and it had 6,100 likes and evoked varied reactions for acknowledging Narendra Modi “inspires us to work relentlessly towards the betterment of the society”.

Some saw the tweet as an insult to father of the nation, Mahatma Gandhi. It also led to a series of memes and discussions online, especially on Twitter.

A week later, when the Twitteri had moved on from this “discovery of a new father of the nation”, the US president stirred things up by calling Modi “father of India” at the Howdy Modi event in Texas on September 23, 2019⁸.

The US President Donald Trump said: “I remember India before was very torn. There was a lot of dissension; fighting and he brought it all together. Like a father would. Maybe he is the father of India.” Prime Minister Narendra Modi did not correct him.

In India, his comment caused a furore. Supporters of Narendra Modi were jubilant. It did not matter that Trump himself was in the centre of a controversy with a formal impeachment inquiry against him “charging him with betraying his oath of office and the nation’s security by seeking to enlist a foreign power to tarnish a rival for his own political gain.”

Reacting to this, Congress leader Jairam Ramesh said the US President calling Prime Minister Narendra Modi “Father of India” is an insult to Mahatma Gandhi. This time, the discussion leaped out of Twitter and other social media sites to find its place in mainstream media.

⁸ Press Trust of India (Sept 25, 2019). “Donald Trump calling PM Modi father of India insult to Mahatma Gandhi: Jairam Ramesh”. India Today, retrieved from <https://www.indiatoday.in/india/story/donald-trump-calling-pm-modi-father-of-india-insult-to-mahatma-gandhi-jairam-ramesh-1603166-2019-09-25>

It was as if some of the leaders of Bhartiya Janta Party were waiting for Modi's endorsement as father of the nation from an international figure. In a TV news debate with Kanhaiya Kumar, Sambit Patra was heard saying "Baap hain Modi, humaare nahi, poore desh ke baap hai Modiji (Modi is father, not just our father but the father of the whole country)"⁹

Just before the 2019 elections, All India Anna Dravida Munnetra Kazhagam (AIADMK) minister, the then Tamil Nadu minister for Milk and Dairy Development KT Rajendra Balaji had said, "Modi is our daddy, he is our daddy, India's daddy."¹⁰ Union minister Jitendra Singh went on to say "those who do not feel proud of US President Donald Trump's comment that Prime Minister Narendra Modi is the "father of India", do not consider themselves Indians."¹¹

Earlier, Khadi Village Industries Commission (KVIC) had published a calendar and diary in 2017 with the cover photo of showing Modi weaving khadi on a large charkha in the same classic pose as Mahatma Gandhi. The BJP Cabinet Minister in the Government of Haryana, Anil Vij, had clarified that "after khadi stationary, Mahatma Gandhi would be removed from notes as well. PM Modi is a bigger brand name than Mahatma Gandhi for khadi...Khadi is not patented in the name of Mahatma Gandhi."¹² If the attempt to replace collective memory is not explicit yet, days after the 150th birth anniversary of Mahatma Gandhi, a private school in Gandhinagar, that also gets government grants, asked Class 9 students during an internal assessment examination: "How did Gandhiji commit suicide?"¹³

In 2017, National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT) syllabus was revised after 15 years to include Modi government's policies such as Swatchha Bharat Abhiyan and demonetisation. In 2018, the government appointed a committee of scholars to prove that Hindus descended from India's first inhabitants. According to news reports, this "Hindu first" version of Indian history will replace the Aryan invasion theory in school curriculum¹⁴.

There is a shift in the narrative and it is not merely decolonising school syllabuses but a larger scheme to replace collective memories to promote a specific narrative. Narratives preserved by collective memory often play a normative role in shaping or correcting actions in authorising and criticising ethical and political proposals (Knapp, 1989). In the age of new media and online archives, an advance search on

⁹ Video retrieved from YouTube <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=DtRVsWfHkh4&t=227s>

¹⁰ Scroll staff (Mar 9, 2019), "Tamil Nadu: 'Modi is our daddy, India's daddy,' claims AIADMK minister", Scroll, retrieved from <https://scroll.in/latest/915988/tamil-nadu-modi-is-our-daddy-indias-daddy-claims-aiadmk-minister>

¹¹ Press Trust of India (Sept 25, 2019), "Those Not Proud of Modi Being Called 'Father of India' Aren't Indians: Union Minister. The Wire, retrieved from <https://thewire.in/politics/those-not-proud-of-modi-being-called-father-of-india-arent-indians-union-minister>

¹² FE Online (Jan 14, 2017), "Mahatma Gandhi will be removed from currency as well, Modi a bigger brand: Anil Vij, Haryana Minister". Financial Express, retrieved from <https://www.financialexpress.com/india-news/narendra-modi-has-bigger-brand-image-mahatma-gandhi-will-be-removed-from-currency-as-well-anil-vij-haryana-minister/507772/>

¹³ Press Trust of India (Oct 14, 2019). "How did Gandhiji commit suicide: Gujarat school shocks students with question". India Today, retrieved from <https://www.indiatoday.in/india/story/how-did-gandhiji-commit-suicide-gujarat-school-shocks-students-with-question-1609076-2019-10-14>

¹⁴ Sharma K (Aug 9, 2019). "Modi govt plans NCERT syllabus change again, this time a major one", The Print, retrieved from <https://theprint.in/india/education/modi-govt-plans-ncert-syllabus-change-again-this-time-a-major-one/274854/>

Google or any other internet browser is enough to give a rough estimate of the frequency of word usage. The results are not accurate but provide a rough estimation that substantiates my argument in this paper.

A preliminary google search of the phrase “Modi is the father of” appears 51,900 times while “Gandhi is the father of” appears 92,100 times. Despite immense academic, journalistic and other textual mentions of Gandhi since the birth of internet in India, ‘Modi is the father of’ appears more than half the times ‘Gandhi is the father of’ does.

Search terms	Frequency
Modi is the father of	51,900
Gandhi is the father of	92,100
“Narendra”, “Modi” and “Respect”	59,90,000
“Mahatma”, “Gandhi” and “Respect”	97,70,000
“Manmohan”, “Singh” and “Respect”	18,50,000
“Rahul”, “Gandhi” and “respect”	41,50,000
Manmohan Singh is the father of	25,200

A google search of “Manmohan Singh is the father of” gives appears 25,200 times even when he is known as the father of reform process in India. Modi appears 51,900 when searched with “is a father of”. The words ‘Narendra’, ‘Modi’ and ‘Respect’ appears together or combined in 59,90,000 google search results while ‘Mahatma’, ‘Gandhi’ and ‘Respect’ appears 97,70,000 times.

When searched with the name of former prime minister Manmohan Singh, ‘Manmohan’, ‘Singh’ and ‘Respect’ appears 18,50,000 times and when searched with Congress leader Rahul Gandhi’s, ‘Rahul’, ‘Gandhi’ and ‘respect’ appears 41,50,000 google search results.

The data collected for Narendra Modi and Rahul Gandhi was then compared using the custom time range function in the Google search tools. This showed that the frequency of the word ‘respect’ in texts associated with Rahul Gandhi was higher than Manmohan Singh because besides using the word as any other individual would, Gandhi also reacted or quoted Narendra Modi in public speeches.

This data indicates how the use of the word ‘respect’ has increased in the recent years, especially after 2014, the year Narendra Modi was elected to power. This further justifies my argument that the current political regime is fixated with ‘respect’.

The twitter hashtag that stayed among the top 10 trends for two days on January 16-17, 2010, #RespectYourPM illustrates the desire for political hegemony. The hashtag was started by Zee News, pro-government TV news channel, during its debate I have discussed in my paper earlier.

The hashtag, in its explicit hierarchal language ('respect your PM' instead of 'Respect our PM'), demanded respect for Prime Minister Narendra Modi in the wake of anti-CAA protests. The words that appeared most frequently in the tweets and retweets with this hashtag were: "Modi", "Cong", "Nation", "Ours".

The Twitter advert that announced the start of the hashtag received a paltry 60 likes and 13 retweets but the hashtag was soon taken over by the social media team of BJP, that was running online campaign ahead of the Delhi assembly elections, that stated using #RespectYourPM with #हममोदीजीकेसाथहैं (#WeAreWithModiJi).

An analysis of a set of 1000 live tweets under #RespectMyPM collected on January 17 showed most of the tweets were from India and United States. Top keywords in the tweets were 'Pakistan',

'Stop', 'Congress Army', 'Human' and 'Spite'. Top keywords in the twitter profile were 'Jay', 'Dharma', 'Indian', 'Rashtra', 'Modi' and 'Politics'.

Following a manual by Global Investigative Journalist Network (GIJN) to identify twitter trolls, it was found in the analysis that most of the tweets and retweets using #RespectYourPM was by trolls who amplified tweets in support of Narendra Modi and BJP.

This section on 'father of new India' discusses attempts to shape public memory by occupying the central position of a "father-figure" who cannot be questioned because of the imaginary sacrifices he has made.

In Foucault's disciplinary society, bodies and minds are trained to conform under 'strict methods of control'. Systems of monitoring and control spread through all social institutions: schools, workplaces, and the family. A patriarch, as the Prime Minister is being projected as, commands respect and through this hegemonic position he controls.

Of the gods and goddess of Indian politics

Deriving from Gramscian idea of religion as a hegemonic force, the religious rhetoric and iconography has a crucial role to play in political adherence and control over popular imagination. Within Hindu practice, the enormous stress on visuality endows a great range of images with extra ordinary power and the images are politically effective because of their ubiquity (Pinney, 2004).

This explains why mythological and religious rhetoric has always driven political populism in India so much so that the religious chant of 'Jai Shree Ram (victory to Lord Ram)' has now become political slogan for the right-wing in India. The expression that was an inextricably a part of Hindu practices in Northern India, which people even used to greet each other, is now a rallying cry for religious violence.

After the late 1980s TV series Ramanand Sagar's Ramayan, the actors who played the characters on screen were given party ticket and their popularity not just helped parties during the campaigning but also in winning elections. Attempts to iconify Ram and Krishna in the political spheres been persistent through textual and verbal allusions and through various media including posters and hoardings.

Narendra Modi started appearing as Krishna just before the 2007 Gujarat assembly elections in several unofficial party advertisements.

In 2012, Narendra Modi was depicted as Lord Krishna in a BJP advertisement published in a local newspaper in Gujarat. The advertisement was placed by local BJP leader Bharat Kamdar, who headed the party's branch in the Amreli district. The ad also shows Gujarat BJP President R C Faldu as Arjun and party leaders Vijay Rupani, Purshottam Rupala and IK Jadeja as the Pandavas. This was repeated again before the 2014 elections.

Addressing a rally in Bihar before the 2014 general elections, Narendra Modi said: “The descendants of Krishna’s Yaduvansh should not worry; I am here to take care of them. Krishna had gone to Dwarka from Mathura; I have come from Dwarka to take care of you, have no worries.”¹⁵ In a rally in Imphal, he said: “Lord Krishna was married to a women in the Northeastern. Rukmini was from the Northeast and Krishna lived in Gujarat.”¹⁶

On January 27, 2016, BJP MP Paresh Rawal compared Modi’s charisma with that of Lord Ram. Addressing students of Nirma University during a programme, Rawal said like the stones with Lord Ram's name on them floated on water in Ramayana, Modi’s name ensured victory of the BJP in the 2014 General Elections.¹⁷

In the wake of surgical strikes in Pakistan occupied Kashmir in the same year, posters came up in Varanasi depicting Modi as Ram and Pakistan PM Nawaz Sharif as Ravana. The posters were put up by the local unit of Shiv Sena and showed a Ram-like Modi pointing arrow at ten-headed Ravana (Nawaz Sharif). Delhi chief minister Arvind Kejriwal, who was under fire for demanding proof of surgical strike

¹⁵ [NarendraModi.in](https://www.narendramodi.in/od/narendra-modi-addresses-the-people-of-bihar-highlights-the-need-to-make-india-congress-free-6096) (Apr 4, 2014). “[Narendra Modi addresses the people of Bihar, highlights the need to make India Congress-free](https://www.narendramodi.in/od/narendra-modi-addresses-the-people-of-bihar-highlights-the-need-to-make-india-congress-free-6096)”, retrieved from <https://www.narendramodi.in/od/narendra-modi-addresses-the-people-of-bihar-highlights-the-need-to-make-india-congress-free-6096>

¹⁶ Pisharoty SB (Mar 31, 2018), “NE Dispatch: The Distortion of Manipur's History and Assam's Debate on Citizenship”, The Wire, Retrieved from <https://thewire.in/politics/ne-dispatch-the-distortion-of-manipurs-history-and-assams-debate-on-citizenship>

¹⁷ Zee News (Jan 28, 2016). “Paresh Rawal compares PM Narendra Modi with Lord Ram, says his name ensured BJP's victory in 2014”, retrieved from https://zeenews.india.com/news/india/paresh-rawal-compares-pm-narendra-modi-with-lord-ram-says-his-name-ensured-bjps-victory-in-2014_1850011.html

in PoK, was also shown as machete-wielding Meghnad (demon son of Ravana, the main antagonist in Hindu epic Ramayana). The text on the poster reads: “One more surgical operation is required to finish Ravana-like Pakistan.”

On February 16, 2017, at a rally in Uttar Pradesh, Modi, in election mode, had said like Lord Krishna, he was adopted by the state of Uttar Pradesh, which he considers to be his "mai-baap (mother and father)" and he now wished to serve it like a true son.

Chief minister of Uttar Pradesh, Yogi Aditya Nath has been portrayed as Ram, Hanuman and even Chhatrapati Shivaji.

By 2017, several other political parties woke up to the appeal of such advertisements. Congress portrayed Rahul Gandhi as Arjun, Ram, Shiva, Krishna and Priyanka Vadra as Durga and Modi as Mahisasur and Ravan. Samajwadi party portrayed Akhilesh Yadav as Vishnu. All such posters have their leaders as the hero and the adversaries are given the role of the demon. Meanwhile, on social media sites, several poems in the form of religious couplets, praising the religious leaders, are actively shared and promoted.

Respect and obedience in the trans-mediated world

Many scholars have emphasised on personalistic autocracies are built through sustained conditioning of perception of a leader as an icon. The image of a coherent leader is pieced together through various symbols, narratives and social media campaign. Normalisation of hegemony is a process and has several layers and stages. It is imperative for political obedience that reverence towards a leader is impressed upon as a nationalistic duty. Thus, an opposite thought of being critical of a political leader is made to be believed as seditious. We respect something not because we want to but because we have to (Wood 1999) and it involves the experience that “one must pay attention and respond appropriately” (Birch 1993). Respect thus demands yielding, a sort of compromise, when the subject feels obligated to obey the object’s demand - an antithesis of a democracy. So, unlike autocratic or dictatorial regimes where this domination or control is explicit, governments in new democracies implant reverence and control through circuitous manipulation of narratives, as I have delineated in my article.

This process of policing political expression of the masses becomes a challenge in post-media era when the greatest rebellion emerge out of what Rancière called ‘distribution of the sensible’. Nothing makes sense anymore. In the Deleuzian world of cyborgs, these narratives fail because of the heightened visibility in the post-mediated world.

I could see the various political banners, using religious iconography, in different part of the country with a simple google search. In just a fraction of a second, my computer screen is filled with hundreds of images, each a spectacle, that I soon in or zoom out. I use the archived media artefact, sans its geography, and map connections between them. Baudrillard said that the legacy of the current epoch is “the obscenity of the visible, of the all-too-visible, of the more-visible-than-the-visible”. To this manipulations of respect towards the political leaders, emerges a new language of protest, manifesting Appadurai’s disjuncture in the mediascape - the social media memes.

The analysis of tweets under #RespectMyPM reveals a defiant subculture that borders on obscenity and sophistication, of humour and gravity. In their tackiness, they put out potent political statements, they not just diffuse the authoritative tone of political propaganda but make them look silly.

Abuse, a crucial aspect of ‘unofficial language’ and ‘heteroglossia’, debases the dominant ‘verbal-ideological life of the nation and the epoch’ through play, ridicule and seeming obscenity (Bakhtin, 1981).

The outrageous posters and placards at a protest cite and the memes are no different in their ambition but non-seriousness of the memes helps it escape censure and at the same time, their online virality give the message wider mobility.

However, it also makes one wonder - for how long? In the superabundant hyperrealities of the online sensorium strips messages of their intention, be it a political narrative or its counter-narrative, what emerges is a white noise with individuals in their filter bubbles.

My paper maps out these little conflicts of the contemporary.

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